

Review

Chaga (*Inonotus obliquus*) in Healthspan: An Integrative Perspective of Naturopathy and Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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Abstract: Chaga mushroom (*Inonotus obliquus*) has been recognized for its medicinal properties and health benefits for centuries, particularly in Eastern Europe and Russia. Chaga is known for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties, and is commonly consumed as a food mushroom due to its high content of antioxidants, proteins, minerals, fiber, and vitamins. Studies suggest its potential in neuroprotection, cancer therapy, and immune-related conditions. While Chaga is generally considered safe, there are potential risks associated with prolonged use and high concentrations of certain compounds. Integration of Chaga in Naturopathy and Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) emphasizes its role in promoting healthy aging and longevity by tonifying the Kidneys, strengthening *Qi*, and calming the *Shen*.

This review explores the multifaceted biological activities of Chaga, emphasizing its potential as a preventive and therapeutic agent in various health conditions. By bridging traditional knowledge with emerging scientific evidence, it underscores the role of Chaga in healthspan.

Keywords: Chaga; *Inonotus obliquus*; Naturopathy; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Aging.

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1. Introduction

Aging consists in a multifactorial process of molecular and cellular decline that we all experience with time ¹. This aging process depends on many factors, such as genetic, dietary and pharmacological intervention and environmental conditions. These factors compromise fate and rate of aging ².

In fact, how the living being responds to daily stress, challenges and insults is strictly related to the aging process ^{3,4}. Having that said, healthy aging refers to the retard process of the cellular and molecular decline for the maximum period which leads to longevity ³⁻⁷.

To achieve longevity and healthy aging is important to understand lifestyle and environmental factors and understand which patterns link to disease prevention and maximizes health ⁸. A form of primary care medicine that integrates traditional healing practices with modern scientific advancements and contemporary research is Naturopathy and TCM ^{9,10}.

Naturopathy practice is guided by a unique set of principles that acknowledge the body's inherent ability to heal itself, emphasize the prevention of disease, and promote individual responsibility in achieving optimal health ¹⁰. Whereas TCM represents a structured healthcare system derived from extensive clinical observation and experimentation, underpinned by a scientific framework of regulation. TCM encompasses distinctive theories and methodologies aimed at disease management and health optimization ^{11,12}.

Mushrooms are utilized as therapeutic agents in both Naturopathy and TCM. These fungus have been widely consumed in the human diet as a supplementary food since

ancient times. They are a rich source of secondary metabolites, vitamins, minerals, protein, and carbohydrates, as well as being high in fiber and low in fat. Additionally, they contain various bioactive compounds such as terpenoids, steroids, phenols, nucleotides, glyco-protein derivatives, and polysaccharides, which make them potential sources of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity¹³. These compounds are responsible for the medicinal properties of the mushroom, making it valuable for therapeutic applications¹⁴. Medicinal mushrooms and their bioactive preparations are considered nutraceuticals, used for health promotion and disease prevention. Producing them requires knowledge of mushroom species, as well as control over cultivation and processing to ensure safety and effectiveness¹⁴. However, its high cost and cultivation difficulties limit its availability in diets¹³.

Inonotus obliquus is a Basidiomycetes species found in birch forests of Russia, Korea, Europe, the USA, and Canada. It is known by various names, including "Gift from God" in Siberia and "King of Plants" in China¹³. This fungus is a sterile fungus that destroys trees and parasitizes the trunks of live birch trees. It belongs to the Hymenochaetaceae family and thrives in humid regions^{15,16}. The *Obliquus* species is known for its medicinal and pharmacological properties¹⁷.

Chaga sclerotium grows on the trunks of old birch trees, from which it absorbs medicinal compounds, including betulin and betulinic acid, which are derived from the birch trees themselves. These bioactive compounds contribute to Chaga's therapeutic effects¹. Like others medicinal mushrooms, Chaga has been recognized for its healing properties in both traditional and modern medical practices¹⁸.

Most *I. obliquus* populations form fruiting bodies, which take 10–15 years to mature for medicinal use. To overcome this, artificial methods like liquid fermentation are used to grow *I. obliquus* mycelia, offering shorter production cycles and higher yields. Submerged fermentation is particularly effective for producing biomass and bioactive compounds, including exo-polysaccharides. Recent studies have optimized this process for enhanced production of bioactive polysaccharides¹⁹. Globally, Chaga is recognized for its therapeutic benefits and the discovery of new bioactive metabolites for use in pharmaceutical, chemical, and cosmetic products²⁰.

2. A Naturopathic perspective on Chaga

2.1. Traditional use

Chaga sclerotium has a long history of medicinal use in Eastern Europe, with records indicating its use dating back to at least the 12th century. Historical accounts suggest that the Russian duke Vladimir Monomach reportedly cured himself of lip cancer using Chaga. The Khanty people, an indigenous group from Siberia, traditionally utilized this mushroom in beverages and meals to enhance vitality and prevent degenerative diseases¹.

The preparation methods of Chaga in indigenous herbal and non-medicinal uses vary between tribes and cultures. In some tribal practices, Chaga is used to enhance immune function and treat conditions such as diabetes and tumors¹⁸. This mushroom is commonly consumed as a food mushroom, as it is rich in antioxidants, proteins, minerals, fiber, and vitamins¹⁸.

2.2. Pharmacological properties

Only the young and fresh sclerotia of *Inonotus obliquus*, specifically those found on birch trees and collected year-round, are considered suitable for medicinal use²¹. It is essential that the sclerotia are harvested from pristine, unpolluted environments, as the fungus has the potential to absorb environmental contaminants²². This species naturally thrives in regions with harsh climatic conditions, including extreme seasonal temperature variations, freezing winters, exposure to ultraviolet radiation, and frequent bacterial or viral challenges^{23,24}. To adapt to such environmental stressors, *I. obliquus* has developed

sophisticated defense strategies, producing a range of bioactive compounds such as antioxidants, triterpenoids, ergosterol derivatives, sesquiterpenes, benzoic acid derivatives, hispidin analogs, and melanins ²¹.

Inonotus obliquus exhibits pharmacological properties, including potent antioxidant ²⁵, immunomodulatory ²⁶ and anti-inflammatory activities ^{27,28}. These properties make it a valuable natural compound in the fight against aging and the enhancement of healthspan.

Antioxidant properties

Antioxidants play a critical role in mitigating oxidative damage to biomolecules by reducing reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels, thereby protecting body cells from harm caused by free radicals. Free radicals interact destructively with biomolecules, contributing to the onset of diseases such as cancer ²⁹, aging ³⁰ and atherosclerosis ^{31,32}. By inhibiting free radical attacks, antioxidants can prevent lipid oxidation within cell membranes, enhancing the cellular defense mechanisms against damage ³².

The polysaccharides extracted from Chaga exhibit significant antioxidant activity through their ability to scavenge superoxide radicals ^{33,34}. This mechanism is thought to occur via the donation of hydrogen atoms by the polysaccharides, which combine with free radicals to form a stable radical. This process effectively terminates the harmful chain reactions caused by oxidative stress, thereby protecting cells from damage. Such antioxidant properties are crucial in reducing oxidative damage, which is linked to aging and various chronic diseases ^{33,34}. For instance, a comparative study demonstrated that ethanol extracts inhibit superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity, and a higher DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) scavenging ability compared to hot water extracts. Hot water extractions, particularly at elevated temperatures, also display enhanced antioxidant capabilities ³⁵.

The antioxidant activity of Chaga extends to neuroprotection ³⁶. A study from 2011 demonstrated that Chaga extract improved cognitive function in scopolamine-induced amnesia in mice, increasing endogenous antioxidants such as glutathione and superoxide dismutase levels, and enhancing memory and learning abilities ³⁶.

The neuroprotective effects of flavan derivatives, polysaccharides, and 3,4-dihydroxybenzalacetone isolated from *Inonotus obliquus* have been demonstrated in models of neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's, as well as in the SH-SY5Y cell line ^{10,13,37}. These substances have been found to mitigate oxidative stress and promote the upregulation of superoxide dismutase (SOD) expression ²⁵.

A study demonstrated that birch sap (*Betula alba*) and extracts from *Inonotus obliquus* exhibit potent antioxidant properties by preventing the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and mitigating oxidative stress induced by UV irradiation ³⁸. Furthermore, the tested compounds displayed immunomodulatory effects, as evidenced by a reduction in pro-inflammatory cytokine levels following UV exposure ³⁸. The extracts also contributed to the protection of keratinocytes by decreasing UV-induced DNA damage ³⁸. These findings highlight the photoprotective potential of *Betula alba* sap and *Inonotus obliquus* extracts in skin cells exposed to UV-A and UV-B radiation ³⁸. Given their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and DNA protection/repair activities, these bioactive compounds represent promising candidates for the development of cosmetic formulations aimed at counteracting photoaging ³⁸.

The antioxidant properties of Chaga are particularly crucial in mitigating the effects of oxidative stress, a primary driver of aging and the onset of age-related diseases. As we age, the body's ability to neutralize free radicals diminishes, leading to cellular damage and the accumulation of oxidative stress ³⁹. By neutralizing ROS, Chaga reduces oxidative damage to cells, protecting cellular integrity and contributing to longevity and healthspan ³⁹.

Immunomodulatory Properties

The immunomodulatory effects of Chaga can counteract the decline in immune function associated with aging. As the immune system weakens over time, individuals become more susceptible to infections, autoimmune disorders, and chronic inflammatory conditions²¹. Polysaccharides derived from mushrooms are potent biologically active compounds that significantly enhance both innate and adaptive immune responses, positioning them as promising immunostimulators. Their potential extends to various clinical and medicinal applications, offering opportunities for therapeutic interventions in immune-related conditions⁴⁰⁻⁴².

Polysaccharides isolated from sclerotia, and submerged culture mycelia have also been utilized as immune-enhancing agents, functioning as biological response modifiers (BRMs) that stimulate both cellular and humoral immunity⁴³. These immunomodulatory effects likely contribute to their antitumor activity. Clinically, polysaccharides, like β -glucans, have been widely employed in cancer therapies for their immunomodulatory benefits⁴³.

Additionally, triterpenoid compounds extracted from Chaga have demonstrated significant anticancer properties, including the inhibition of cancer cell proliferation, induction of cell cycle arrest at various checkpoints and enhancement of apoptosis^{44,45}. These compounds also regulate key signal transduction pathways involved in cellular growth and survival, making them potential candidates for cancer therapy. Notably, the triterpene inotodiol has been shown to exhibit antihistamine-like effects by inhibiting mast cell degranulation in the small intestine, providing a potential therapeutic avenue for managing food allergies in animal models^{44,45}.

Anti-inflammatory Properties

Studies have shown that Chaga extracts effectively reduce inflammation markers, suggesting their potential in managing chronic inflammatory conditions that hinder healthspan. Macrophages, which play a key role in inflammation, can release mediators such as nitric oxide (NO), prostaglandins (PGE2) and pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6)⁴⁶. Studies on methanol extracts of Chaga demonstrated their capacity to inhibit macrophage activity, reducing the production of NO, PGE2 and cytokines⁴⁶.

In a study from 2012, aqueous Chaga extracts significantly alleviated dextran sodium sulfate (DSS)-induced colitis⁴⁷. The extracts reduced edema, mucosal damage and crypt loss while suppressing the expression of inflammatory cytokines and lowering levels of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS)⁴⁷. Furthermore, they decreased the accumulation of myeloperoxidase in the colon, indicating reduced inflammatory activity⁴⁷.

Aqueous Chaga extracts suppress the expression of inflammatory mediators such as p53, caspase-3 and microcystin-LR, which contribute to inflammation and hepatotoxicity in mice. Another highlighted the ability of Chaga extracts to mitigate carbon tetrachloride (CCl4)-induced liver damage. Ergosterol peroxide isolated from Chaga was shown to bind and inhibit the activity of pro-inflammatory proteins, further confirming its anti-inflammatory efficacy⁴⁸.

Additionally, betulin and betulinic acid, compounds found in *Inonotus obliquus*⁴⁹, have demonstrated notable anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties. These compounds modulate immune cell activities and inhibit the production of pro-inflammatory mediators, suggesting their therapeutic potential for inflammatory disorders⁵⁰.

A chemical investigation of the fruiting bodies of *Inonotus obliquus* identified seven novel lanostane-type triterpenoids (inonotusols H-N), all of which inhibited NO production in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated BV-2 microglial cells. Inonotusols I and L showed the strongest suppression of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) and NO production without cytotoxicity. Molecular docking confirmed their interaction with iNOS, highlighting their anti-inflammatory potential⁵¹.

Finally, the anti-inflammatory properties of Chaga are critical in managing the chronic inflammation that accelerates aging. Chronic low-grade inflammation, often referred to as "inflammaging," is linked to the development of cardiovascular diseases, arthritis, and neurodegenerative diseases^{13,38}. By modulating the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and reducing inflammation, Chaga helps mitigate these risks, thereby contributing to a healthier aging process. Inflammation is a key driver of many age-related diseases, and by addressing this underlying issue, Chaga offers a natural means of promoting healthy aging^{13,38}.

3. A Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) Perspective on Chaga

Aging is described in The Yellow Emperor's Classic of Chinese Medicine as a natural physiological process that is intrinsically linked to the balance of *Yin* and *Yang*, the smooth flow of *Qi* (vital energy), and the preservation of *Jing* (vital essence)⁵². While aging occurs progressively over time, it can be significantly accelerated by factors such as emotional imbalances, poor lifestyle choices, and the depletion of *Jing*, which is stored in the kidneys and consumed throughout life⁵².

The depletion of *Jing* is associated with both physical and mental decline. To mitigate premature aging, it is crucial to focus on preserving *Jing*, strengthening *Qi*, and maintaining a balanced and harmonious lifestyle⁵². This includes adopting practices such as regular meditation, moderate physical activity (e.g., *Qi Gong* or Tai Chi), and adhering to a nutrient-dense diet tailored to the body's constitution and seasonal variations⁵². Within the framework of TCM, healthy aging emphasizes vitality, mental clarity, and physical health achieved through a holistic and integrative approach⁵². Aging is regarded as a natural part of life that should be embraced, with the goal of fostering inner harmony, preserving energy, and aligning one's life with the rhythms of nature to achieve a graceful and fulfilling aging process⁵².

Chaga mushroom is well-known for its "white rot" characteristics and has traditionally been consumed as a functional tea for its benefits in combating aging and promoting longevity⁵³. *Inonotus obliquus* has a flavor described as slightly bitter and possessing a somewhat cold nature. This combination of taste and characteristics reflects its functional properties in traditional Chinese medicine, which considers the relationship between flavor and therapeutic effect. Bitterness is often associated with effects that may help to "drain" or "dry out" conditions in the body, while the cold nature is linked to properties that may assist in reducing heat and detoxifying the body⁵⁴.

Within TCM, *Inonotus obliquus* is recognized for its medicinal properties, particularly its role in strengthening the immune system and enhancing the body's resilience to disease. From an energetic perspective, Chaga is considered an adaptogenic mushroom that supports immune function, strengthens *Qi*, tonifies the Kidneys (which are considered the reservoir of vital essence or *Jing*), protects the Liver, strengthens the Stomach, calms the Heart, and soothes the *Shen* (spirit). Additionally, Chaga is noted for its detoxifying properties, which make it particularly beneficial in cases of Kidney energy exhaustion, rendering it appropriate for long-term use⁵⁵. This mushroom further promotes blood circulation, reduces blood stasis (exhibiting analgesic effects) therefore tonifying the Heart, protecting the Liver, and revitalizing *Qi*⁵⁵.

4. Practical Application and Safety Considerations

Since antiquity, the use of *Inonotus obliquus* and its crude extracts has been regarded as generally harmless¹⁸. Despite the significant attention garnered by its bioactive properties over the last decade, the safety and toxicology of Chaga remain underexplored. The limited studies available present divergent perspectives on the mushroom's safety¹⁸.

Several studies affirm the safety of Chaga for consumption by both animals and human⁵⁶. For instance, research has demonstrated that alcohol-based and aqueous extracts of Chaga do not adversely affect primary porcine hepatocytes (PLP2) at a concentration

of 400 ppm compared to cells exposed to alcohol alone⁵⁷. Additionally, other investigations report no significant effects on body weight, liver, or kidney functions in Kunming mice and Sprague-Dawley rats exposed to Chaga extracts^{56,58}.

Also, it is already known that concentration of 20–160 µg/mL of IOPS do not produce toxicity and are safe to administer this dose⁵⁹. There is another study about the toxicity of *Inonotus obliquus* polysaccharides-chromium (III) where it was administering daily doses of 1500 mg/kg and after four weeks later, the results showed 10% of formalin on liver, pancreas and kidney⁶⁰.

In opposition, some studies suggest potential risks. A study reported that ethanol extracts of Chaga were cytotoxic to HaCaT keratinocyte cells at concentrations ranging from 100 to 400 µg/mL. Furthermore, varying levels of oxalic acid, a toxic compound found in Chaga, have been documented^{57,61,62}. Despite, when the ethyl acetate fraction does not contain pure IOPS (*Inonotus obliquus* polysaccharide) and only parts of it, it's safe to say that *Inonotus obliquus* ethyl acetate fraction is nontoxic⁶³.

Therefore, the consumption of medicinal mushrooms should be cautious, as their safety during pregnancy, lactation, and in children is still poorly understood⁶⁴. Bioactive compounds found in mushrooms may affect the absorption of nutrients, vitamins, and trace elements⁶⁴. Therefore, it is recommended that the elderly and children avoid excessive consumption⁶⁴. Additionally, individuals taking medications or herbs should be careful when consuming mushrooms due to the risk of interactions with their bioactive compounds⁶⁴.

In fact, nowadays, Chaga mushroom has a wide range of pharmacological uses and so there are many ways to presenting it as a health product such as, healthy food products, teas, tablets, tinctures, capsules and beverage, according to some ecommerce platforms^{21,59}. The different applications of Chaga are because there are varied functions as well⁶⁵. Depending on the brand and the application form, it's possible to obtain diverse benefits from preventing and treating diabetes or enhance immunity to anti allergic function⁶⁵. Despite that, infusions and inhalation are the most common and traditional ways of use internally and antiseptic soaps externally⁶⁶.

The overuse of natural fungi, including Chaga, is a growing concern among medical experts⁶⁷. Nutritional and environmental factors influencing the host also significantly impact the chemical composition and safety of Chaga⁵⁹. Given these complexities, adhering to stringent safety and health regulations is critical to ensure the safety and efficacy of Chaga products⁵⁹.

Further toxicological studies are necessary to authenticate their safety and support their application in treating various conditions⁵⁹. To improve and guarantee the quality of Chaga products (health food or pharmacological products) the brands must have implemented the ISO22000:2018 and the HACCP methodology⁵⁹.

5. Conclusion

This narrative review highlights the potential of Chaga in mitigating age-related cellular and molecular decline. Its polysaccharides, triterpenoids, and phenolic compounds have demonstrated significant antioxidant activity, reduced oxidative stress and protected against neurodegenerative processes. Additionally, its immunomodulatory effects suggest benefits in maintaining immune system balance, while its anti-inflammatory properties may contribute to reducing chronic inflammation, a key driver of aging and age-related diseases. These studies provide scientific evidence supporting the relationship between the pharmacological properties of Chaga and healthy aging, highlighting its therapeutic potential in promoting longevity and preventing age-related diseases.

From a naturopathic perspective, Chaga aligns with the principles of supporting the body's intrinsic healing capacity, on the other side, TCM recognizes its potential in promoting balance and for promoting healthy aging and longevity.

Despite its promising health benefits, challenges remain regarding the sustainable sourcing, standardization, and bioavailability of Chaga-based products. Further research

is necessary to elucidate its precise mechanisms of action, optimal dosages, and long-term effects on human health. Nevertheless, the evidence reviewed suggests that Chaga may serve as a valuable natural ally in promoting healthspan, warranting further scientific exploration and integration into complementary medicine practices.

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References

1. Pizzorno JE, Murray MT. Textbook of Natural Medicine: Textbook of Natural Medicine: Elsevier Health Sciences; 2020. 0323523803.
2. López-Otín C, Blasco MA, Partridge L, Serrano M, Kroemer G. The hallmarks of aging. *Cell*. 2013;153(6):1194-217.
3. Pérez VI, Buffenstein R, Masamsetti V, Leonard S, Salmon AB, Mele J, et al. Protein stability and resistance to oxidative stress are determinants of longevity in the longest-living rodent, the naked mole-rat. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 2009;106(9):3059-64.
4. Johnson T, Cypser J, De Castro E, De Castro S, Henderson S, Murakami S, et al. Gerontogenes mediate health and longevity in nematodes through increasing resistance to environmental toxins and stressors. *Experimental gerontology*. 2000;35(6-7):687-94.
5. Miller RA, Buehner G, Chang Y, Harper JM, Sigler R, Smith-Wheelock M. Methionine-deficient diet extends mouse lifespan, slows immune and lens aging, alters glucose, T4, IGF-I and insulin levels, and increases hepatocyte MIF levels and stress resistance. *Aging cell*. 2005;4(3):119-25.
6. Smith ED, Kaerberlein TL, Lydum BT, Sager J, Welton KL, Kennedy BK, et al. Age- and calorie-independent life span extension from dietary restriction by bacterial deprivation in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *BMC developmental biology*. 2008;8:1-13.
7. Lin Y-J, Seroude L, Benzer S. Extended life-span and stress resistance in the *Drosophila* mutant methuselah. *Science*. 1998;282(5390):943-6.
8. Ayyadevara S, Alla R, Thaden JJ, Shmookler Reis RJ. Remarkable longevity and stress resistance of nematode PI3K-null mutants. *Aging cell*. 2008;7(1):13-22.
9. Silva R, Lima da Fonseca M. Medicinal Mushrooms in Mental Health: A Review of TCM and Naturopathy. 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13353840>
10. Fleming SA, Gutknecht NC. Naturopathy and the primary care practice. *Primary Care: Clinics in Office Practice*. 2010;37(1):119-36.
11. Matos LC, Machado JP, Monteiro FJ, Greten HJ. Understanding Traditional Chinese Medicine Therapeutics: An Overview of the Basics and Clinical Applications. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2021;9(3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9030257>
12. Rodrigues JM, Santos C, Ribeiro V, Silva A, Lopes L, Machado JP. Mental health benefits of traditional Chinese medicine – An umbrella review of meta-analyses. *Brain Behavior and Immunity Integrative*. 2023;2:100013. doi: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2023.100013>

13. Debnath T, Park SR, Kim DH, Jo JE, Lim BO. Anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of *Inonotus obliquus* and germinated brown rice extracts. *Molecules*. 2013;18(8):9293-304.
14. Ern PTY, Quan TY, Yee FS, Yin ACY. Therapeutic properties of *Inonotus obliquus* (Chaga mushroom): a review. *Mycology*. 2024;15(2):144-61.
15. Razumov EY, Safin R, Mukhametzyanov SR, Baigildeeva E, Safina A, Lebedev D, editors. Studies of the composition of the cryogenic ground chaga. IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering; 2020: IOP Publishing.
16. Abu-Reidah IM, Critch AL, Manful CF, Rajakaruna A, Vidal NP, Pham TH, et al. Effects of pH and temperature on water under pressurized conditions in the extraction of nutraceuticals from chaga (*Inonotus obliquus*) mushroom. *Antioxidants*. 2021;10(8):1322.
17. Balandaykin ME, Zmitrovich IV. Review on chaga medicinal mushroom, *Inonotus obliquus* (higher basidiomycetes): Realm of medicinal applications and approaches on estimating its resource potential. *International Journal of Medicinal Mushrooms*. 2015;17(2).
18. Fordjour E, Manful CF, Javed R, Galagedara LW, Cuss CW, Cheema M, et al. Chaga mushroom: a super-fungus with countless facets and untapped potential. *Frontiers in pharmacology*. 2023;14:1273786.
19. Xue J, Tong S, Wang Z, Liu P. Chemical characterization and hypoglycaemic activities in vitro of two polysaccharides from *Inonotus obliquus* by submerged culture. *Molecules*. 2018;23(12):3261.
20. Peng H, Shahidi F. Qualitative analysis of secondary metabolites of chaga mushroom (*Inonotus Obliquus*): phenolics, fatty acids, and terpenoids. *Journal of Food Bioactives*. 2022;17.
21. Szychowski KA, Skóra B, Pomianek T, Gmiński J. *Inonotus obliquus*—from folk medicine to clinical use. *Journal of traditional and complementary medicine*. 2021;11(4):293-302.
22. Shashkina MY, Shashkin P, Sergeev A. Chemical and medicobiological properties of chaga. *Pharmaceutical Chemistry Journal*. 2006;40(10):560-8.
23. Bolwell PP, Page A, Piślewska M, Wojtaszek P. Pathogenic infection and the oxidative defences in plant apoplast. *Protoplasma*. 2001;217:20-32.
24. Zucconi L, Ripa C, Selbmann L, Onofri S. Effects of UV on the spores of the fungal species *Arthrotrrys oligospora* and *A. ferox*. *Polar Biology*. 2002;25:500-5.
25. Seo H-K, Lee S-C. Antioxidant activity of subcritical water extracts from Chaga mushroom (*Inonotus obliquus*). *Separation Science and Technology*. 2010;45(2):198-203.
26. Kim Y-R. Immunomodulatory activity of the water extract from medicinal mushroom *Inonotus obliquus*. *Mycobiology*. 2005;33(3):158-62.
27. Kim H-G, Yoon D-H, Kim C-H, Shrestha B, Chang W-c, Lim S-y, et al. Ethanol extract of *Inonotus obliquus* inhibits lipopolysaccharide-induced inflammation in RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. *Journal of Medicinal Food*. 2007;10(1):80-9.
28. Nagajyothi P, Sreekanth T, Lee J-i, Lee KD. Mycosynthesis: antibacterial, antioxidant and antiproliferative activities of silver nanoparticles synthesized from *Inonotus obliquus* (Chaga mushroom) extract. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*. 2014;130:299-304.
29. Takaki A, Yamamoto K. Control of oxidative stress in hepatocellular carcinoma: helpful or harmful? *World Journal of Hepatology*. 2015;7(7):968.
30. Briehl MM. Oxygen in human health from life to death—An approach to teaching redox biology and signaling to graduate and medical students. *Redox biology*. 2015;5:124-39.
31. Ellinsworth DC. Arsenic, Reactive Oxygen, and Endothelial Dysfunction. *The Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*. 2015;353(3):458-64. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1124/jpet.115.223289>

32. Wang B-S, Chang L-W, Yen W-J, Duh P-D. Antioxidative effect of sesame coat on LDL oxidation and oxidative stress in macrophages. *Food chemistry*. 2007;102(1):351-60. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2006.05.026>
33. Huang S-q, Ding S, Fan L. Antioxidant activities of five polysaccharides from *Inonotus obliquus*. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2012;50(5):1183-7.
34. Mu H, Zhang A, Zhang W, Cui G, Wang S, Duan J. Antioxidative properties of crude polysaccharides from *Inonotus obliquus*. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2012;13(7):9194-206.
35. Hu H, Zhang Z, Lei Z, Yang Y, Sugiura N. Comparative study of antioxidant activity and antiproliferative effect of hot water and ethanol extracts from the mushroom *Inonotus obliquus*. *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*. 2009;107(1):42-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiosc.2008.09.004>
36. Giridharan VV, Thandavarayan RA, Konishi T. Amelioration of scopolamine induced cognitive dysfunction and oxidative stress by *Inonotus obliquus* – a medicinal mushroom. *Food & function*. 2011;2(6):320-7. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1FO10037H>
37. Zou C-X, Wang X-B, Lv T-M, Hou Z-L, Lin B, Huang X-X, et al. Flavan derivative enantiomers and drimane sesquiterpene lactones from the *Inonotus obliquus* with neuroprotective effects. *Bioorganic chemistry*. 2020;96:103588.
38. Softa M, Percoco G, Lati E, Bony P. Birch sap (*Betula alba*) and chaga mushroom (*Inonotus obliquus*) extracts show anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory and dna protection/repair activity in vitro. *Journal of Cosmetics, Dermatological Sciences and Applications*. 2019;9(2):188-205.
39. Park YK, Lee HB, Jeon EJ, Jung HS, Kang MH. Chaga mushroom extract inhibits oxidative DNA damage in human lymphocytes as assessed by comet assay. *Biofactors*. 2004;21(1-4):109-12.
40. Borchers AT, Krishnamurthy A, Keen CL, Meyers FJ, Gershwin ME. The immunobiology of mushrooms. *Experimental biology and medicine*. 2008;233(3):259-76.
41. Moradali M-F, Mostafavi H, Ghods S, Hedjaroude G-A. Immunomodulating and anticancer agents in the realm of macromycetes fungi (macrofungi). *International immunopharmacology*. 2007;7(6):701-24.
42. Han X-Q, Chung Lap Chan B, Dong C-X, Yang Y-H, Ko C-H, Gar-Lee Yue G, et al. Isolation, Structure Characterization, and Immunomodulating Activity of a Hyperbranched Polysaccharide from the Fruiting Bodies of *Ganoderma sinense*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2012;60(17):4276-81. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf205056u>
43. Wasser S. Medicinal mushrooms as a source of antitumor and immunomodulating polysaccharides. *Applied microbiology and biotechnology*. 2002;60:258-74.
44. Nguyet TMN, Lomunova M, Le BV, Lee JS, Park SK, Kang JS, et al. The mast cell stabilizing activity of Chaga mushroom critical for its therapeutic effect on food allergy is derived from inotodiol. *International immunopharmacology*. 2018;54:286-95.
45. Zhao F, Xia G, Chen L, Zhao J, Xie Z, Qiu F, et al. Chemical constituents from *Inonotus obliquus* and their antitumor activities. *Journal of natural medicines*. 2016;70:721-30.
46. Im KH, Nguyen TK, Choi J, Lee TS. In Vitro Antioxidant, Anti-Diabetes, Anti-Dementia, and Inflammation Inhibitory Effect of *Trametes pubescens* Fruiting Body Extracts. *Molecules* [Internet]. 2016; 21(5). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules21050639>
47. Mishra SK, Kang J-H, Kim D-K, Oh SH, Kim MK. Orally administered aqueous extract of *Inonotus obliquus* ameliorates acute inflammation in dextran sulfate sodium (DSS)-induced colitis in mice. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 2012;143(2):524-32.
48. Ishfaq PM, Mishra A, Mishra S, Ahmad Z, Gayen S, Jain SK, et al. *Inonotus obliquus* Aqueous Extract Suppresses Carbon Tetrachloride-induced Hepatic Injury through Modulation of Antioxidant Enzyme System and Anti-inflammatory Mechanism. *Clinical Cancer Drugs*. 2021;8(2):122-36. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2174/2212697X08666211130130119>
49. Plehn S, Wagle S, Rupasinghe HV. Chaga mushroom triterpenoids as adjuncts to minimally invasive cancer therapies: A review. *Current Research in Toxicology*. 2023;5:100137

50. Oliveira-Costa JF, Meira CS, Neves MVGD, Dos Reis BPZC, Soares MBP. Anti-Inflammatory Activities of Betulinic Acid: A Review. *Frontiers in pharmacology*. 2022;Volume 13 - 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.883857>
51. Zhang W, Zhang Y. Characteristics of potential effects and benefits of inonotus obliquus from the perspective of traditional Chinese medicine. *International Journal of Traditional Chinese Medicine*. 2019;776-80.
52. Kou R-W, Han R, Gao Y-Q, Li D, Yin X, Gao J-M. Anti-neuroinflammatory polyoxygenated lanostanoids from Chaga mushroom *Inonotus obliquus*. *Phytochemistry*. 2021;184:112647.
53. Veith I. *The Yellow Emperor's Classic of Internal Medicine*: University of California Press; 2015. 9780520963245.
54. Wei Y-M, Yang L, Wang H, Cai C-H, Chen Z-B, Chen H-Q, et al. Triterpenoids as bivalent and dual inhibitors of acetylcholinesterase/butyrylcholinesterase from the fruiting bodies of *Inonotus obliquus*. *Phytochemistry*. 2022;200:113182. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2022.113182>
55. Rodrigues R, Rodrigues P, Murteira A. PRONTUÁRIO Fitoterapia Chinesa. 2023;V001.00.1123.
56. Yong T, Chen S, Liang D, Zuo D, Diao X, Deng C, et al. Actions of inonotus obliquus against hyperuricemia through XOD and bioactives screened by molecular modeling. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2018;19(10):3222.
57. Glamočlija J, Ćirić A, Nikolić M, Fernandes Â, Barros L, Calhelha RC, et al. Chemical characterization and biological activity of Chaga (*Inonotus obliquus*), a medicinal “mushroom”. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 2015;162:323-32. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2014.12.069>
58. Nakata T, Yamada T, Taji S, Ohishi H, Wada S-i, Tokuda H, et al. Structure determination of inonotsuoxides A and B and in vivo anti-tumor promoting activity of inotodiol from the sclerotia of *Inonotus obliquus*. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*. 2007;15(1):257-64.
59. Chen H, Liou B-K, Hsu K-C, Chen C-S, Chuang P-T. Implementation of food safety management systems that meets ISO 22000:2018 and HACCP: A case study of capsule biotechnology products of chaga mushroom. *Journal of Food Science*. 2021;86(1):40-54. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.15553>
60. Wang C, Chen Z, Pan Y, Gao X, Chen H. Anti-diabetic effects of *Inonotus obliquus* polysaccharides-chromium (III) complex in type 2 diabetic mice and its sub-acute toxicity evaluation in normal mice. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*. 2017;108:498-509.
61. Kikuchi Y, Seta K, Ogawa Y, Takayama T, Nagata M, Taguchi T, et al. Chaga mushroom-induced oxalate nephropathy. *Clinical nephrology*. 2014;81(6):440-4.
62. Lee S, Lee HY, Park Y, Ko EJ, Ban TH, Chung BH, et al. Development of end stage renal disease after long-term ingestion of Chaga mushroom: case report and review of literature. *Journal of Korean medical science*. 2020;35(19).
63. Gao X, Santhanam RK, Xue Z, Jia Y, Wang Y, Lu Y, et al. Antioxidant, α -amylase and α -glucosidase activity of various solvent fractions of *I. obliquus* and the preventive role of active fraction against H₂O₂ induced damage in hepatic L02 cells as fungisome. *Journal of Food Science*. 2020;85(4):1060-9.
64. Łysakowska P, Sobota A, Wirkijowska A. Medicinal mushrooms: Their bioactive components, nutritional value and application in functional food production—A review. *Molecules*. 2023;28(14):5393.